

Tools to assess from different perspectives the feasibility of power barge solutions to supply electricity to vessels - The BlueBARGE Project concept

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Abstract

The BlueBARGE Project addresses the design, development, and demonstration of an optimum power-barge solution to provide electricity to moored and anchored vessels, limiting emissions in a life cycle perspective, following a modular, scalable, and flexible design approach. The proposed power-barge solution considers different power system alternatives in the form of containerised power supply modules in a variety of configurations, where battery modules will serve as the basis due to their high energy efficiency and readiness level, supported by other alternative energy sources, such as hydrogen fuel cells.

BlueBARGE introduces a novel hybrid energy concept that combines the higher energy density of lithium (Li-ion) batteries with the innovative Vanadium Redox Flow Battery (VRFB) solution, which introduces increased safety and lifespan. Inverters, power distribution units and interfacing systems will be crucial for the power-barge alternative design and promoted solution, covering approximately the 20% of the available barge footprint considering only a single level of containers, along with other barge utilities, such as additional mooring and berthing equipment. The rest will be mostly covered by power supply modules. The design will follow a modular and scalable approach to support different use cases, different ship types and power requirements.

Alternative designs are assessed via a multi-objective framework: first, specific KPIs are defined and a multi criteria analysis framework is created. Then, the solutions are compared from technical, environmental, and economical criteria, using quantitative and qualitative values provided by experts. An optimization tool is also developed with the objective of providing optimal sizing alternatives from a multicriteria perspective. Finally, the promoted selection is studied following a detailed cost analysis. This paper describes the assessment framework with a holistic approach and its possibilities for assessing solutions and concepts for offshore and harbour electrification of marine vessels.

Introduction to the BlueBARGE Project

The BlueBARGE Project, funded by the European Union (EU) Horizon Europe Programme, brings together an international multidisciplinary Consortium with the aim of **designing, developing and demonstrating an Innovative Power Barge Solution for moored and anchored vessels** to be commercially viable by 2030. By doing so, the project aligns with and supports the goals of electrification and decarbonisation in the maritime industry at EU and international level.

Figure 1. The BlueBARGE Project concept.

The Project has identified and described **ten Use Cases** where the BlueBARGE solution would be feasible, that are described in the following Table:

Table 1. The BlueBARGE Project Use Cases.

Use Case	Description
UC1: Anchored Vessels	The process of delivering electricity to vessels moored offshore, ensuring a continuous and monitored power supply from the barge to the ship.
UC2: Moored Vessels	Utilizing a power-barge to provide electricity to ships moored offshore, especially in ports lacking SSE infrastructure or to supplement existing SSE systems.
UC3: Isolated inhabited areas	Supporting isolated seaside regions or islands with underdeveloped local power grids.
UC4: Environmentally critical areas	Provide clean electricity in environmentally critical areas, enhancing sustainability and environmental preservation
UC5: Charging of small transportation vessels	Providing a reliable source of electricity to vessels, ensuring decarbonization of Inland Waterway Transport vessels

UC6: Powering leisure boats along the coast	Clean electricity for leisure boats in popular nautical tourism hubs, particularly in the Mediterranean Sea.
UC7: Powering offshore platforms – oil rigs	Electrification solutions for offshore oil and gas platforms, reducing reliance on diesel engines and traditional grid connections.
UC8: Charging from offshore power plants	Use of the power generated at the offshore wind power stations by delivering to hybrid or full electric vessels on route.
UC9: Providing power to land after natural disaster events	Enhance emergency response and recovery by ensuring a reliable power supply in the aftermath of natural disasters.
UC10: Charging BlueBARGE from anchored vessels	Internal combustion generation optimization on vessels by providing necessary energy balancing.

Assessment tools for a Hybrid Battery Energy Storage System on a barge

The assessment framework consists of the following developments:

1. The definition of an assessment framework. In this task, lead by NTUA, the **multi-criteria assessment framework has been described, introducing the definition of different KPIs** to evaluate at a high level, for all the identified Use Cases, the different design alternatives that have been produced in the Project, associating environmental impacts, costs, risks and technical feasibility criteria.
2. The **assessment of the alternative designs to obtain a promoted solution**, based on the framework and KPIs previously defined, implemented in an alternatives evaluation web tool that evaluates the suitability of each alternative to each of the Use Cases, based on the opinion from relevant experts and external stakeholders.
3. An **advanced assessment tool that provides optimal sizing configurations** for a power-barge solution, based on the design alternatives and the preferences and needs indicated by potential investors and parties interested in providing the service.
4. An in-detail **cost-benefit assessment of the promoted BlueBARGE solution**, following the established framework, in a life cycle perspective, considering the results of the pilot demonstrations.

Figure 2. The assessment tools developed in BlueBARGE and their interaction.

The developments are briefly described next.

BlueBARGE Assessment & Optimization Framework

The BlueBARGE Assessment and Optimisation framework aims to assist decision-makers in understanding the attributes of the alternative designs to meet operational requirements while providing an analytical foundation for evaluating the performance attributes, as documented in subsequent materialisation phases of the project. In essence, it highlights the capabilities and commercial value of the alternatives. The assessment results will empower stakeholders to discuss the appropriate trade-offs among cost, schedule, performance, and risk and evaluate the operational capabilities and affordability of the alternative designs developed in the Project. Ultimately, these results will guide decision-makers in shaping and scoping courses of action for new material solutions to address operational capability needs and developing the roadmap for the development phase of the promoted design. The goal was to create the framework for assessing the design alternatives for the power-barge concept for the identified use cases (high-level assessment). The assessment aimed for a promoted design alternative, which will be later further examined and optimised.

Thus, the task was focused on setting-up the assessment and design optimisation framework, which drives both the high-level and later the in-detail level assessment. As an example of the work done, the following Table displays the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined for the design alternatives of BlueBARGE:

Table 2. KPIs defined to assess the alternative designs.

KPI description
KPI 1.1 Verify identified use cases
KPI 1.2 Complete at least 5 alternative design cases for power-barge concept
KPI 1.3 Scalable solution should be able to cover 95% of commercial fleet of container ships and passenger vessels, including cruise ships, of at least 5,000 GT
KPI 1.4 Achieve at least 3MW discharge power and 35MWh power capacity through the BlueBARGE promoted design
KPI 2.1 Achieve an at least 500kW discharge power through the prototype
KPI 2.2 Achieve an at least 1.5MWh capacity through the prototype
KPI 2.3 Cover energy demand of demonstration vessel for at least 1 hour
KPI 3.1 Showcase emission reduction through at least 10 environmental KPIs
KPI 3.2 Reduction in GHG and other polluting emissions from vessels in anchorage will be presented in detail for at least two use cases scenarios
KPI 3.3 Showcase the reduction of noises and vibrations up to 80% during barge service, compared with the actual onboard energy generation
KPI 4.1 At least 20% net savings from investing in BlueBARGE
KPI 4.2 At least 10 stakeholders declared interest on the BlueBARGE concept and design
KPI 4.3 Limited – or even non – conflict with regulatory framework
KPI 5.1 Issue NTQ Statement of Maturity for all innovations
KPI 5.2 Address all identified high-risk areas with at least 1 risk control measure
KPI 5.3 Approval-in-principle by classification society granted
KPI 5.4 Operational and safety guidelines reviewed and verified by all relevant industry partners

Assessment of the alternative designs and optimum design

The evaluation process in this tool builds directly on the assessment methodology defined in the previous task. This methodology provides a rigorous, multi-criteria foundation for screening, scoring, and ranking design alternatives through a structured sequence of goal definition, criteria identification, and performance measurement. It employs Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis MCDA techniques, complemented by sensitivity and cost-capability analyses, to balance environmental, technical, financial, and safety considerations. Importantly, this approach ensures that only alternatives meeting key threshold KPIs are advanced to full evaluation, thereby securing objectivity and comparability. The application of this methodology in the assessment tool guarantees that the optimum BlueBARGE design is selected based on transparent, evidence-driven analysis, aligned with project decarbonisation goals.

The overall goal is to come up with the best fit BlueBarge design among different alternatives as depicted and characterized in the Project (that are described below) while meeting the predefined KPIs and thresholds.

The tool developed allows each expert to grade the alternatives for each criterion either with crisp numbers (e.g. 1-10) or using linguistic values in a five-degree Likert scale ranging from Very Low (VL) to Very High (VH), or even with absolute numbers (e.g. cost). The criteria are characterized as cost or benefit and the assessment could be Numeric (N), Linguistic (L), Objective (O), or Subjective (S). Additionally, experts assign weights to reflect both the relative importance of criteria and their own expertise level.

ENVIROMENTAL [Toggle](#)

Exp. Imp.

Feasibility Assessment

Please, rank the Barges from an Environmental point of view (CO₂, NO_x, SO_x, PM) and per Use Case:

UMBRELLA CASE 1						
ENVIROMENTAL	UC1: Anchored Vessels <small>Emissions during navigation toward the anchored area and charging/loading electricity/hydrogen area. Towing emissions if not self-propelled. Mooring boat involved. Origin of the energy.</small>	UC4: Environmental critical areas <small>Judgments of the target and charging/testing electricity/hydrogen area. Towing emissions if not self-propelled. Mooring boat involved. Origin of energy.</small>	UC5: Charging of small transportation vessels <small>Assessing inland waterways transport. Towing emissions if not self-propelled. Mooring boat involved. Origin of energy. Services alongside the river and at inland ports. Electric barge concept included.</small>	UC8: Charging from offshore power plants and wind farms <small>Emissions from offshore power plants and wind farms (renewable electricity charged but might not hydrogen charging there); to vessels in the surroundings. Towing assistance if not self-propelled and mooring both sides.</small>	UC10: Charging Bluebarge from outer anchored vessels <small>Transfer electricity from one vessels to the barge in order to provide with electricity different customers. Emissions during navigating distances. Towing assistance if not self-propelled and mooring boat emissions. Can be combined with other use cases.</small>	
Barge Design 1.1	<input type="text" value="3* Medium of emissions saved"/>	<input type="text" value="4* Lower of emissions saved"/>	<input type="text" value="2* Higher of emissions saved"/>	<input type="text" value="1* The Highest of emissions saved"/>	<input type="text" value="3* Medium of emissions saved"/>	
Barge Design 1.2	<input type="text" value="3* Medium of emissions saved"/>	<input type="text" value="4* Lower of emissions saved"/>	<input type="text" value="2* Higher of emissions saved"/>	<input type="text" value="1* The Highest of emissions saved"/>	<input type="text" value="3* Medium of emissions saved"/>	
Barge Design 1.3	<input type="text" value="3* Medium of emissions saved"/>	<input type="text" value="4* Lower of emissions saved"/>	<input type="text" value="2* Higher of emissions saved"/>	<input type="text" value="1* The Highest of emissions saved"/>	<input type="text" value="3* Medium of emissions saved"/>	
Barge Design 1.4	<input type="text" value="3* Medium of emissions saved"/>	<input type="text" value="4* Lower of emissions saved"/>	<input type="text" value="2* Higher of emissions saved"/>	<input type="text" value="1* The Highest of emissions saved"/>	<input type="text" value="3* Medium of emissions saved"/>	
Barge Design 2.6	<input type="text" value="3* Medium of emissions saved"/>	<input type="text" value="4* Lower of emissions saved"/>	<input type="text" value="2* Higher of emissions saved"/>	<input type="text" value="1* The Highest of emissions saved"/>	<input type="text" value="3* Medium of emissions saved"/>	
Barge Design 3.3	<input type="text" value="3* Medium of emissions saved"/>	<input type="text" value="4* Lower of emissions saved"/>	<input type="text" value="2* Higher of emissions saved"/>	<input type="text" value="1* The Highest of emissions saved"/>	<input type="text" value="3* Medium of emissions saved"/>	

1* The Highest of emissions saved ... 6* N/A

Figure 3. Web assessment tool interface.

Advanced optimal sizing configurations tool

The objective is to provide a set of possible configurations in size and combination of power units for the BlueBARGE, based on the needs and preferences entered by a potential operator of the service. The power barge is ideally powered by batteries and hydrogen fuel cells to ensure zero emissions, with the sizing of these components being the primary focus of the optimization. The system must be capable of meeting varying energy and power demands effectively, economically, and within the spatial and operational constraints. The following Figure depicts the initial approach for the system modelling, with input and output variables that will be used

to minimize an objective function that takes into consideration the investment needed, the energy capacity estimated, and the service provided. The joint sizing and dispatch optimization problem is formulated as a mixed-integer nonlinear program in Python.

Figure 4. System modelling for the optimal sizing tool.

In-detail cost-benefit assessment of the promoted BlueBARGE solution

This task will focus on the final full-scale design of the power-barge, based on the promoted solution from the assessment done. The activities will involve an in-detail assessment of the solution, following the established framework, in a life cycle perspective, and the results of the pilot demonstrations. Environmental performance will be crucial for both GHG and local emissions, while CBA will again evaluate the integrated system in terms of financial KPIs, including environmental costs. The CBA output will support the development of business cases and assist in the commercialization roadmap of the BlueBARGE.

Figure 5. In-detail cost-benefit assessment of the promoted BlueBARGE solution.

The BlueBARGE alternative designs and the promoted selection

Six different design alternatives have been produced as possible designs for the BlueBARGE solution. All the alternatives include a hybridization of Li-ion and VRF batteries, with different combinations of number of units and capacity. The other variables considered for the design are the size of the barge (three different sizes have been considered), the use or not of hydrogen fuel cells and tanks, and whether to use a self-propelled barge or a towed one. All the six alternatives meet the KPI objectives defined in the Project and defined previously in this document. The six alternatives are described in the following Table:

Table 3. The BlueBARGE design alternatives defined in the Project.

Name	Size (m)	Self Propelled	Hydrogen fuel tanks	Li-ion units	VRFB units	Total energy capacity (MWh)
1.1	97x23x4	No	No	33	14	70.3
1.2	97x23x4	Yes	No	33	14	65.3
1.3	97x23x4	No	40	4	2	147.3
1.4	97x23x4	Yes	40	4	2	142.3
2.6	48x17.7x2.75	No	10	2	1	38.8
3.3	61.5x12x4.5	No	10	5	2	43.3

The web assessment tool has been used to evaluate the six alternatives and select the promoted solution that will be analysed in detail in the BlueBARGE Project. The evaluation has been performed by a selection of internal and external stakeholders and experts.

The analysis indicates that **Design 1.2** achieved the highest overall score, demonstrating balanced performance across technical, environmental, financial, and safety dimensions for the different Use Cases. Design 1.4 followed closely, also scoring favourably across most criteria, particularly in terms of safety performance. Conversely, Designs 3.3 and 2.6 obtained the lowest scores, reflecting comparatively weaker alignment with the evaluation criteria and stakeholder expectations.

Figure 6. Ranking of the Alternative Designs visualized in a bar chart.

Conclusions

The BlueBARGE Project offers a sustainable, fossil-free alternative towards decarbonisation and is dedicated to delivering a modular, scalable, adaptable and flexible design approach. The proposed approach/rationale sets the environmental aspects derived from the project activities as the focal point of the decision-making process. In addition, the barge can be used for different Use Cases identified, such as offshore power supply services in ports where the grid capacity is limited. Additionally, BlueBARGE could be used to ensure the resilience of the local grid in the event of a disruptive event or high demand.

The assessment framework aims to identify the most environmentally advantageous barge design among available alternatives developed in the Project and the leading reasonably-priced and competitive technology for electricity supply, considering the significant external costs involved. It also includes the establishment of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and provides arguments that stimulate decision-making discussions in assessing the different alternatives and optimum design. The established methodology facilitates further engagement from different perspectives, considering the stakeholders' roles, opinions, and interests.

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